

SCENARIOS

**Strategies for health protection, pollution
Control and Elimination of Next generAtion
Refractive Organic chemicals from the Soil,
vadose zone and water**

<https://scenarios-project.eu/>

This project has received funding from the European Union's H2020 programme under Grant Agreement N°. 101037509.

SCENARIOS is a 4-year H2020 Research and Innovation project (RIA) involving 19 partners from 10 European countries and Israel. The goal is to close the knowledge gap and achieve breakthrough TRL advances in the toxicology, detection and remediation of probably the most objectionable and widespread class of contaminants -PFAS, with an unprecedented energetic balance and virtually no external chemical additives. A major effort is underway to develop Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment (IATA) of PFAS, including the new generation of congeners, to assist EC and EU countries in decision-making on these substances for environmental safety and human health.

PFAS SMART DETECTION - HAZARD & RISK ASSESSMENT - DECONTAMINATION

What are PFAS? PFAS are persistent organic pollutants also known as “forever chemicals” because can remain in the environment for long. They can accumulate in living organisms and pose a high risk to human health and environment.

Persistent organic pollutants (POPs) are usually mobile, being transported between multiple environmental compartments such as soil, groundwater and, surface waters. Alternatively, semi-volatile POPs can be atmospherically long-range transported to reach remote areas such as polar regions or high mountains. Chemical substances that have been historically identified as POPs are -for example- chlorinated pesticides, dioxins, and furans.

In the last decade, Per- and polyFluoroAlkyl Substances (PFAS) have become part of the POP's list as they are environmentally persistent, potentially carcinogens and display a high bioaccumulation rate. Currently, PFAS are detected in multiple environmental matrices (soil, sediment, biota, air dust, food, drinking water) and can be found inside the human body (blood) more frequently than you might expect. Furthermore, the chemical structure of PFAS congeners and their chemo-physical features pose a technological challenge to environmental remediation technologies.

SCENARIOS provides a complete set of sustainable solutions to protect human health, the environment, and natural resources from persistent and mobile chemicals, and PFAS. In recent years the presence of toxic pollutants in the environment has increased along with the awareness of their potentially adverse effects on human health. Environmental contaminant exposure significantly contributes to the development of diseases such as cancer, vascular, neurodegenerative illness, inflammatory diseases, allergies, and immune system disorders, which

constitute the main health burden in economically developed countries. Exposure to chemical pollutants occurs through the food chain, drinking water, skin contact and the inhalation of airborne particles.

Pollution also causes serious damage to ecosystems and ecosystem services such as water purification, the nutrient cycle, biodiversity, and crop yields accounting for costs potentially exceeding the current EU GDP that will be paid by future generations.

IMPACTS

SCENARIOS aims to devise and demonstrate a comprehensive set of technological solutions to address the detection, (bio)monitoring, long-term toxicity, risk assessment, pollution control and remediation of Per- and PolyFluoroAlkyl Substances (PFASs) as a test bed for zero pollution ambition from refractory and mobile organic chemicals.

SCENARIOS's approach and technologies will be self-sustainable, (near) net-zero energy and will smoothly integrate in the circular economy concept of EU countries and worldwide.

KNOWLEDGE SHARING

A harmonized composition of the project consortium encompassing renewed academic and research centers as well as competitive technological SMEs will ensure SCENARIOS' value at continental level and beyond. The project will fill the knowledge gap and deliver disruptive remediation TRL advancements for probably the most awkward and widespread toxic class of contaminants -PFAS- with unprecedented energetic balance and the near absence of external chemical additions.

SCENARIOS will promote EU leadership in the sector and provide a significant advance in the research field.

The industrial core of SCENARIOS will enable four demonstrations (case studies) within functioning EU industrial sites and a public health institution, putting forward a set of industrial and societal outcomes where pollutant remediation and health surveillance offer excellent potential for the Green Deal implementation.

GREEN DEAL SUPPORT

SCENARIOS aims at contributing to the Green Deal goal stated as “zero pollution ambition for a toxic free environment”. The project will evaluate and develop cutting-edge technologies and strategies for detection, quantification, control, and elimination of PFAS from soil, vadose zone and water by pursuing outcomes within the 4 remediation quadrants: In-situ soil, In-situ water, Ex-situ soil and Ex-situ water. Likewise, the project devises a set of pollution control and remediation solutions for PFAS- contaminated drinking water, agricultural soil and groundwater. All these solutions will conform to the principle of green chemistry, (near) zero energy, sustainability and circular economy.

INNOVATIVE KNOWLEDGE

Sustainable, viable, cost effective PFAS monitoring & remediation technologies.

FOCUS of RTD & DEMO

- Detection & Removal of PFAS from groundwaters, drinking water, wastewater, slurries
- Detection & Removal PFAS from soils
- Feasibility and scale-up for field testing
- Human biomonitoring
- Hazard & Risk Assessment for PFAS

FOCUS of DISSEMINATION & EXPLOITATION

Direct actions towards uptake:

- **Replication** and **partner agreements** for post-Project EU-wide exploitation
- **Value chain** supported by exploitation professionals for post-Project uptake
- **Clustering** with ongoing research activities for synergies
- Clear **leveraging** of past and ongoing research at partner organisations.

VIABLE IMPACTS

Technology, Consortium, Stakeholder and Community impacts:

- New technologies for PFAS
- Sustainable water & soil treatment systems
- Communication to 500,000, targeted dissemination and outreach to over 15,000 stakeholders
- Reduction of contamination by PFAS and human health protection
- Support to policy and decisions makers
- Ecosystem restoration & biodiversity protection
- Worldwide scale-up via coordinator

TECHNOLOGIES

In order to evaluate and identify the mechanisms of action and the lifecycle of this class of persistent contaminants, SCENARIOS will use a cross-toxicological approach that includes the study of human and environmental safety by using molecular systems biology, toxicogenomics and phenotypic screening, supported by bioinformatics and cheminformatics.

In order to develop, use and demonstrate such an integrated set of solutions, the following specific objectives have been identified.

Smart detection of PFAS

Implementing a fast, low-cost and accurate determination of PFAS to allow inexpensive widescale measurement and (bio)monitoring of PFAS congeners in any environmental and biological sample.

Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment (IATA) and Environmental Risk Assessment (ERA) for PFAS

Expanding the ERA framework of non-regulated PFAS and congener mixtures on a long-term scale, implementing a specific class of IATA for PFAS.

Innovation for PFAS remediation

Development and implementation of an integrated engineering and biological remediation strategy for cleaning PFAS-contaminated environmental compartments, so as to eventually improve their potential ecosystem service (e.g., soil biodiversity for soil fertility).

PILOT SITES

Technology validation by means of pilot demonstration in the most relevant industry and application.

Bringing together various demo sites across Europe to demonstrate and validate the green performance and the effectiveness of the innovative SCENARIOS solutions when faced with different environmental and technical challenges in relevant real case studies of all selected fields of application:

1

Biomonitoring of PFAS in blood using sensor-based methods. SCENARIOS will operate the first public biomonitoring project in people living in an area notorious for the occurrence of cancers, systemic infections, and neurological disorders in children, and where one of the few PFAS manufacturing facilities in Europe is located, Spinetta Marengo, Alessandria, Italy.

Inhabitants of the Municipality of Montecastello, Frugarolo, Spinetta Marengo and Alessandria are involved. The new developed smart detection technologies based on Surface-Enhanced Raman Spectroscopy (SERS) and /or electrochemistry will be demonstrated.

SCENARIOS Partner Azienda Ospedaliera di Alessandria (AOAL), in the framework of the Piedmont Regional Health System, Italy, will be in charge for this demonstration together with FORTH, BGU and UPO.

2

Remediation of PFAS in groundwater and soil at two sites in Scandinavia. The two polluted sites are characterized by different geological settings and a different PFAS congener composition. The old Albäck landfill in Trelleborg, Sweden, has been used for decades as a fire-fighting training spot by the local fire department. The underground water is characterized by a legacy 3M Aqueous Film Forming Foam fingerprint whose primary component is PFOS.

The second site is in Korsør, Zealand, Denmark. This is a firefighting training school whose underground water shows a short-chain PFAS (C4-C6) signature typical of current AFFF formulations.

SCENARIOS technological solutions such as Surface-Active Foam Fractionation (SAFF), Vadose zone Monitoring System (VMS), and cold plasma destruction, will be demonstrated. Partner ENVYTECH and GEO will be in charge for this multiple pilots together with SENSOIL, BGU, FORTH, UPO, UNILE, UCLM.

3

Remediation of short chain PFAS in drinking water.

Surface-Active Foam Fractionation will be demonstrated as a valuable technique for the removal of legacy and C4-C6 fluoroalkyl congeners at levels below limit of detection in a drinking water treatment plant in Catalonia, Spain. Partner IDP will be in charge for this demonstration through ENVYTECH and FORTH remediation solutions and the external support of local industry.

Italy

Location: Municipality of Montecastello and Spinetta Marengo, Alessandria

Partners: UOAL

Type: Biomonitoring of PFAS in blood using sensor based techniques

Sweden / Denmark

Location: Trelleborg, Sweden & Korsør, Denmark

Partners: ENVITECH & GEO

Type: Remediation of PFAS in groundwater and soil.

Spain

Location: Catalonia

Partners: IDP

Type: High-Performance Surface-Active Foam Fractionation removal of short chain PFAS from drinking water

The **SCENARIOS consortium** is composed of 19 partners from 11 countries: Cyprus, Denmark, Finland, Germany, Greece, Israel, Italy, Luxemburg, Spain, Sweden and United Kingdom.

They conform an interdisciplinary group that brings together methodology, know-how and expertise .

Our project partners have been chosen to form a well-balanced and complementary set of research organisations (RTO's) and innovation focused SME's to enable breakthroughs to the system and its key technologies.

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